

Relapsing Cutaneous PAN with Chronic Hepatitis B: A Rarest Phenomenon

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Abstract

Introduction- Cutaneous polyarteritis nodosa (cPAN) is a rare, chronic, relapsing vasculitis limited to medium-sized vessels of the skin. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a known etiological factor in systemic PAN; however, its association with cPAN is less commonly reported. It triggers symptoms like fatigue, fever, joint pain, abdominal pain, and skin lesions caused by immune complex deposition. HBV-PAN is an immune-complex-mediated disease where viral antigens form complexes that deposit in blood vessels, causing inflammation, thrombosis, and microaneurysms, particularly in the kidneys, skin, and gastrointestinal tract.

Case Report- A 43-year-old female, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with arthralgia for last fifteen years and recurrent painful nodular and ulcerative lesions over the lower limbs for last four years. The last crop of these lesions occurred four months back. The lesions followed a characteristic progression from nodules to purpura, livedo reticularis, and ulceration, healing with scarring. On detailed laboratory investigations revealed elevated inflammatory markers and active Hepatitis B infection. Autoimmune workup was negative. Skin biopsy demonstrated necrotizing medium-vessel vasculitis. The patient was treated with corticosteroids and antiviral therapy, resulting in significant clinical improvement.

Conclusion- Hepatitis B is usually associated with systemic PAN and association with cutaneous PAN is rare. This case highlights the classical relapsing course of cutaneous PAN and emphasizes the importance of screening for Hepatitis B in patients presenting with cutaneous vasculitis. The scientific rationale-based treatment with antiviral and immunosuppressives led to fruitful outcome.

Keywords- Polyarteritis nodosa, Hepatitis B, Ulcer, Purpura, Livedo reticularis

Introduction-

Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) is a necrotizing vasculitis involving medium-sized arteries. It may present as systemic disease or as a localized cutaneous variant. Cutaneous polyarteritis nodosa (cPAN) is characterized by involvement limited to the skin, muscles, and peripheral nerves, with a chronic relapsing course and relatively benign prognosis. Clinically, cPAN presents with tender nodules, livedo reticularis, purpura, and ulcerations, predominantly affecting the lower limbs. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a known etiological factor in systemic PAN; however, its association with cPAN is less commonly reported. PAN

has also been reported with HCV, streptococcal infection and crohn's disease. In systemic PAN in comparison to cutaneous PAN, there is involvement of visceral organs, thus blood pressure is frequently elevated, renal involvement causes proteinuria, eosinophilia & leukocytosis are more frequent, neuromuscular changes are more diffuse and male predominance is more common as compared to cutaneous PAN. p-ANCA is negative in systemic PAN but is positive in cutaneous PAN.

Case Report-

A 43-year-old female, not a known case of any chronic illness presented with arthralgia for last fifteen years involving multiple joints in a symmetrical pattern. The arthralgia was non-deforming and not associated with significant morning stiffness. She developed recurrent painful nodular and ulcerative lesions over the lower limbs for last four years which used to start as erythematous lesions and were treated by local practitioners by oral antibiotics but for no relief. This First episode started on right great toe as tender nodular lesion and progressed to swelling with reddish discoloration, followed by bluish discoloration and eventual ulceration over the dorsal aspect of the foot. The ulcer healed over 5–6 months with residual scarring and hyperpigmentation. During the same period, the patient developed purplish, non-blanching lesions over both upper and lower limbs, suggestive of purpura. There was no history of hematuria, hypertension, abdominal pain, breathlessness, or orthopnea, suggesting absence of systemic involvement. Cutaneous examination revealed multiple tender subcutaneous nodules, non-blanching purpura, livedo reticularis, and ulcerative lesions with necrotic base over the lower limbs. Healed lesions with scarring were also present. Systemic examination was unremarkable. The second episode developed approximately six months later, as the patient developed two painful nodular lesions over the left lower limb, which followed a similar progression from nodules to discoloration and ulceration, healing with scarring over six months. The last crop of these lesions occurred four months back on right lower limb. The lesions followed a characteristic progression from nodules to purpura, livedo reticularis, and ulceration, healing with scarring. The complete hemogram revealed mild normocytic normochromic anemia with hemoglobin of 10.2 g/dL, mild leukocytosis with total leukocyte counts of 13,800/mm³ with normal platelet count. The ESR was significantly raised to 78 mm/hr. and C-reactive protein (CRP) was also elevated. The liver function tests showed mild transaminitis (ALP-82 AST-78 IU/ml) but rest functions were normal. The renal function test, complete thyroid and lipid profile, blood sugar, urine complete, ECG, Chest x-ray, ultrasonogram abdomen were normal. Autoimmune profile showed normal ANA, ASMA, anti LKM antibody and c-ANCA but p-ANCA was weakly positive. The anti HCV and anti-HIV antibody were negative but HbsAg and HbeAg was positive while HbeAb was negative. The HBV DNA was significantly raised to 1,20,000 IU/ml. The skin biopsy from ulcerated lesion revealed segmental transmural necrotizing inflammation of medium-sized vessels with fibrinoid necrosis and neutrophilic infiltrate, consistent with polyarteritis nodosa. Thus, the disease demonstrates a relapsing–remitting course over the past four years. The patient was treated with corticosteroids and antiviral therapy, resulting in significant clinical improvement. We present a case of relapsing cutaneous PAN with a 4-year recurrent course and associated with chronic Hepatitis B infection, highlighting diagnostic and clinical significance.

Figure 1: Clinical photograph showing tender subcutaneous nodule over the lower limb, suggestive of cutaneous vasculitis.

Figure 2: Large cutaneous ulcer over the lower limb,

The differential diagnosis includes microscopic polyangiitis, leukocytoclastic vasculitis and systemic polyarteritis nodosa. These were ruled out based on absence of small-vessel predominance, lack of systemic involvement, and histopathological findings. The patient was started on oral prednisolone (0.75 mg/kg/day) and tenofovir 300 mg once daily along with supportive wound care was provided. The patient showed significant improvement within two weeks, with gradual healing of ulcers over 4–6 weeks. No systemic involvement developed during follow-up.

Figure 3: Healed lesion over the lower limb, indicating relapsing–remitting disease course.

Figure 4- Showing Nodulo-ulcerative lesion in lower limb in Cutaneous PAN Patient with Hepatitis B

Figure 5- Showing livedo reticularis in lower limb in Cutaneous PAN patient with Hepatitis B

Figure 6- Showing Cutaneous lesion on Left ankle at starting and after healing

Discussion-

Poly arteritis nodosa (PAN) associated with hepatitis B (HBV) is a rare, severe, systemic necrotizing vasculitis of small-to-medium muscular arteries [1], often occurring within months of acute infection. It usually occurs between 30-50 yrs of age, especially in lower limbs. It triggers symptoms like fatigue, fever, joint pain, abdominal pain, and skin lesions caused by immune complex deposition. HBV-PAN is an immune-complex-mediated disease where viral antigens form complexes that deposit in blood vessels, causing inflammation, thrombosis, and microaneurysms, particularly in the kidneys, skin, and gastrointestinal tract [2]. The common manifestations include fever, weight loss, severe abdominal pain (due to mesenteric vasculitis), renal infarction, hypertension, cardiac failure, mononeuritis multiplex due to nerve damage, and painful skin nodules or ulcers. The lungs are not usually affected in PAN. The pathogenesis of PAN is not fully understood, but it is thought to be related to an abnormal immune system response [3]. Compared to other systemic vasculitis that have been classified as idiopathic or are truly

autoimmune, PAN has more identified triggering factors. Among these, hepatitis B virus (HVB) is the most frequent and well-characterized trigger of PAN, and the recognition of the etiopathogenic role of HVB in HVB-associated PAN has important therapeutic implications for these patients [1,4]. Along with HVB, hepatitis C virus (HVC), human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), cytomegalovirus, and parvovirus B19 are also suspected as triggering factors of PAN lesions for some patients [4]. It is diagnosed via angiogram showing characteristic aneurysms or by biopsy, often alongside testing for HBsAg-positive hepatitis. Unlike some vasculitides, HBV-PAN is typically ANCA-negative. The preferred treatment is a combination of antiviral drugs (e.g. tenofovir and entecavir), plasma exchanges, and short-term steroids to quickly reduce the viral load and the resulting immune complexes. If left untreated, it is frequently fatal, but with modern antiviral-focused treatment, prognosis has significantly improved. This case demonstrates classical cutaneous polyarteritis nodosa with a chronic relapsing course, sequential lesion progression, and absence of systemic involvement. The long duration of disease (four years) with recurrent episodes strongly supports a diagnosis of cPAN rather than systemic PAN, which typically shows rapid progression with visceral involvement. The association with Hepatitis B suggests immune-complex mediated pathogenesis, although this is more commonly described in systemic PAN. HBV-related vasculitis almost always takes the form of PAN, which can occur at any time during acute or chronic hepatitis B virus infection, although it typically occurs within the first 6 months after infection [5]. HBV-PAN activity does not correlate with that of hepatitis, and the symptoms are identical to those of idiopathic PAN. The major cause of death is gastrointestinal tract involvement, which occurs in 14% to 65% of patients with PAN. The most common symptom is postprandial abdominal pain due to ischemia, and a poor prognosis is associated with it when it is transmural due to the development of necrosis of the bowel wall with perforation [6,7]. Up to 30% of PAN cases were caused by HBV infection [8]. The widespread use of the hepatitis B vaccine and the increased safety of blood transfusions have notably decreased the incidence of HBV-PAN [6], which is now reported to be less than 5% of all cases of PAN [4]. PAN is divided into subacute, acute, and chronic stages. In the subacute stage, mononuclear cell infiltration becomes prominent, while in the acute stage, polymorphonuclear neutrophils infiltrate all layers of the vascular wall [9]. In the chronic stage, the fibrinoid necrosis of the vessels causes thrombosis and tissue infarction. Pulmonary arteries are typically not involved, and bronchial arteries are rarely affected [10]. The treatment for HBV-PAN involves suppressing viral replication with specific antivirals for hepatitis B, such as, entecavir or tenofovir, along with the administration of immunosuppressive medications to control vascular inflammation, such as corticosteroids or other immunosuppressive agents [10].

Conclusion-

Hepatitis B is usually associated with systemic PAN and association with cutaneous PAN is rare. Our case report is rare one where cutaneous PAN was associated with HBV infection. Cutaneous PAN should be suspected in patients with recurrent nodular and ulcerative lesions showing a relapsing course. Screening for Hepatitis B is essential, and early combined therapy leads to favorable outcomes.

Conflict of Interest-

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest and proper consent was taken from patient before publishing this case report. Moreover, no financial support was taken for the same.

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